

Uncertainty analysis of cylinder circumference-to-diameter ratio cut by precision CNC machine and circle cutter

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Uncertainty analysis was performed on precision measurements of cylinders circumference-to-diameter ratios. All measurements yielded circumference-to-diameter=3.144. The measurements were consistent with nine other known measurements. The circumference-to-diameter ratio differed from the assumed theoretical value (in the third digit after the decimal point) of 3.141, for which the author could find no supporting physical measurements (current or historic). The circumference-to-diameter ratio is critical for precision computations of, for example, orbits of Near Earth Objects (NEO). It is also used in most electrical engineering and many engineering computations.

Introduction: Recently more than nine large, 1m and greater diameter, cylinders (from 6 to 12.7mm in height) have been measured (multiple times) by, three independent measurers, using [1, 2] (precision creation, and direct measurement with certified measurement tapes) to determine the circumference (C) to diameter (D) ratio (C/D)). All measurements yielded C/D=3.144.

The methods described in [1, 2] were duplicated, and uncertainty analysis was performed to investigate the claim [1, 2] that (C/D) =3.1446 (equal to 4.0 divided by the square root of the Golden Ratio (1.61803...)).

Several cylinders were independently measured by the author. The cylinder creation and measurement methods described in [1, 2] were followed, duplicated, and investigated.

The cylinders were created by the two methods, precision Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machine, with fine multi-layer plywood, and circle cutter (NT, CL-100P) with foam board. The resulting cylinders circumferences and diameters were measured by a Starrett® Measure Stix™ measuring tape and a NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) certified, individually calibrated PI Tape® [3].

The steel measuring tapes were wrapped around the cylinders and circumference measurements were performed. The PI Tape® featured measurement with a regular scale (calibrated with its own unique tape specific scale serial number), in combination with the Vernier scale (calibrated with its own unique tape specific scale serial number) for maximum accuracy. The circle cutter with foam board created a cut groove (Fig. 1), the width of the measuring tape, into which the measuring tape was inserted. Diameters, for both methods, were measured across the centre of the cylinders. In all measurements (with D=1000mm), excess circumference was >3mm. (C/D) equalled 3.144.

Fig. 1 Top view of circle cutter measurement setup (rectangular foam board, measuring tape inserted in, D=1000mm, cut groove). Foam board clamped to thick flat glass table.

CNC Machine: The CNC machine [4] used to cut cylinders into fine multi-layer plywood, was the Felder Profit H08 (approximately

\$100,000). Special precision cutters were used. Felder technical personnel stated that the machine could cut a 1m by 1m by 1/2inch (12.7mm) thick piece of fine plywood with an accuracy of 0.1mm or better. This applied to any point within the 1 meter square work table. The cutting tool dimensions were stored in the machines software down to 0.01mm. For the uncertainty analysis, the H08 Felder machine was considered to be a ruler with 0.1mm markings.

CNC, (C/D) Ratio Measurement: To measure (C), the steel measuring tape, tensioned to 5 pounds, was placed with the scale towards the centre of (D). The scale facing outward would have incorrectly added to the tape thickness (D). No compression or expansion of the measuring tape was noted, or expected, as the compressive strength (or buckling strength) of steel and tensile strength are very large. They are; steel under tension 210-585 MPa, proportional region, and steel under compression, 159-200 GPa [5].

Tensioned around the cylinders circumference, the beginning ('0') of the Starrett® Measure Stix™ measuring tape measuring tape (Fig.2) met the 3144mm mark. The measurement was duplicated with the PI Tape®. A Vernier measurement indicated the next digit (in C/D, beyond 3.144) was 5.

Fig. 2 Tape circumference (D=1000mm) measurement. Pencil mark (center) at beginning of tape ('0') and at C=3144mm (between 123 and 124 inches). Starrett® Measure Stix™ measuring tape.

Circle Cutter: A second method of creating precision circles was using a circle cutter (center pivot needle on one end, blade on other) with foam board. It was noted that limits to the radii which the user could cut were determined by radial run out play noted at the center pivot point. All other parts of the cutter were fixed and immobile. No other significant contributions to uncertainty were observed.

The two extremes in circle radii potentially created by the user were noted to be pressing radially inward during an entire cutting stroke (minimum radius), and alternatively pulling radially outward during an entire cutting stroke (maximum radius). These two radial extremes were used to compute the circle cutter uncertainty.

Environment: All measurements were made within a 1.5hour time window. Temperature and humidity, were monitored, and did not vary significantly within the measurement time window.

Measurement Uncertainty: Irrespective of the measured data, uncertainty analysis was required to better quantify the measurements. Uncertainties were added linearly on a percentage basis, and in one special case on a mean square basis. The uncertainty from a single measurement, from a single instrument was half the least count of the instrument [6].

The radial uncertainty of the circle cutter had two components, the center pivot pin of the cutter within the cutter itself, and the cutter center pivot pin movement in the foam board. To determine the uncertainty in the circle cutter, it was placed on a clamped down piece of foam board, and the blade end, allowed to float, was placed in contact with a clamped down machinist's dial indicator. The dial indicator delivered precise readings down to 1/1000th of an inch. The dial indicator had an uncertainty of ±0.5/1000inch (±0.0127mm). This uncertainty was included in the total uncertainty, but was relatively insignificant.

The cutter was moved back and forth, and maximum radial run out play of 0-9.5/1000inch, or ±4.75/1000inch (±0.121mm) was measured (over more than 10 measurements). More than five unique center

position holes were measured. If an optional lock nut (M5, metric) was placed on the central pivot pin, this value dropped to $\pm 3/1000$ inch (± 0.0762 mm). The diameter uncertainty was ± 0.0762 mm, and the circumference uncertainty was (C/D) times larger.

Key parameters for the measuring tape uncertainty were obtained from the PI Tape® Calibration Report [3] (Table 1).

Table 1 Summary of key parameters from PI Tape® Calibration Report

About this Calibration		
Tape Tolerance	Within .4mm	(Over length of tape, measurement is within $\pm .4$ mm)
Uncertainty of Measurement	$\pm .10$ mm	(Measurement lab capable of $\pm .10$ mm)

Actual Findings & Procedure Numbers			
Tape Reads	Within .4mm	Over 3000.00mm	(Over length of this tape, measurement within $\pm .4$ mm)
0-10 Scale	Within .2mm	of a true dimension	(Using Vernier, measurement within $\pm .2$ mm)

The (C) and (D) measurement PI Tape® uncertainty, using Vernier scale, was ± 0.2 mm.

Total Uncertainty of Measurement: The total uncertainty of measurement was computed, by adding up the individual percentage uncertainties, given contributions to the total uncertainty were linear. The PI Tape®, CNC Machine, Circle Cutter and Machinist Dial Indicator uncertainties, previously described, were individually entered into the formula for dividing two measurements. The division formula (1) was used to compute the (C/D) uncertainty by dividing the individual (C) and (D) component ($\delta = \pm$) uncertainties [6].

$$\delta = \frac{(C \pm \delta C)}{(D \pm \delta D)} = \left(\frac{C}{D}\right) \left[1 \pm \left(\frac{\delta C}{C} + \frac{\delta D}{D}\right)\right] \quad (1)$$

The computed δ values were then converted to percentage $\pm\%$ uncertainties by dividing by the measured value of (C/D) and multiplying by one hundred (2).

$$\pm\% = \frac{\delta * 100}{\left(\frac{C}{D}\right)} \quad (2)$$

...The total percentage uncertainties were then summed (Table 2, 'Sum Total Uncertainty $\pm\%$ ').

Lastly, the value for total uncertainty of measurement in (C/D) was converted from a percentage, back to an absolute value by multiplying by the measured value of (C/D), and dividing by one hundred. The contributions to the measurement system uncertainty are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Total Uncertainty of Measurement in (C/D)

Uncertainty In (C/D)	CNC	Cutter	Cutter, Nut	(C/D)
C=3144.5mm, D=1000mm				3.1445
PI Tape® $\pm\%$	0.0264	0.0264	0.0264	
CNC Machine $\pm\%$	0.0066			
Circle Cutter $\pm\%$		0.0242		
Circle Cutter, locknut $\pm\%$			0.0152	
Dial Indicator $\pm\%$		0.0025	0.0025	
Sum Total Uncertainty $\pm\%$	0.0330	0.0531	0.0441	
(C/D)= 3.1445 \pm	0.0010	0.0017	0.0014	

The total uncertainty of measurement in (C/D), for the CNC machine was 3.1445 ± 0.001 . The circle cutter measurement was less certain with 3.1445 ± 0.0017 (no center pin locknut), and 3.1445 ± 0.0014 (with center pin locknut).

Total (Mean Square Method) Uncertainty: The above uncertainty analysis over-estimated some of the uncertainties, as simple additions were utilized. In the case of the CNC Machine in combination with the PI Tape®, the machine and the tape measurements were independently calibrated, completely uncorrelated, and linear. We therefore applied mean square uncertainty analysis [7, 8], to this case. The uncertainty was constant over the work table of the CNC machine, and the length of the tape. This made $\delta_C = \delta_D$. The (C) and (D) deltas (δ) were added on a mean square basis (3), with $\delta_{CNC} = \pm 0.05$ mm and $\delta_{PI_TAPE} = \pm 0.2$ mm (using Vernier scale).

$$\delta_{C,D} = \sqrt{(\delta_{CNC})^2 + (\delta_{PI_TAPE})^2} \quad (3)$$

The total (mean square method) uncertainty in (C/D) was then computed (4).

$$\frac{\delta}{\left(\frac{C}{D}\right)} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta_C}{C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta_D}{D}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Multiplying (4) by (C/D), the total (mean square method) uncertainty in (C/D), for the CNC machine with PI Tape®, was 3.1445 ± 0.0007 .

Conclusion: The cylinder creation and measurement methods described in [1, 2] were duplicated, and found to be precise, accurate, and repeatable.

In each case (D=1000mm), an excess circumference of >3 mm was measured, which yielded a cylinder circumference-to-diameter ratio (C/D) of 3.144. This was consistent with nine other known measurements. Using two methods of measurement uncertainty analysis the, theoretical only, value of 3.141 was excluded.

The author was unable to find any physical measurements (modern or historic) that supported a theoretical cylinder (C/D) ratio of 3.141. Further duplication, by physical measurement, and research is urged.

The exact value of the (C/D) ratio is of critical importance for precision computations, such as orbits of Near Earth Objects (NEO).

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September 08, 2020
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